

Business feasibility analysis of ClipMark: A multi-functional stationery product in Bacoor, Cavite

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Abstract

Opportunities for innovation in the sector have been created by the rising demand for stationery products that are both practical and aesthetically pleasing. This study assesses the potential feasibility of ClipMark, a novel multipurpose paperclip, in the Bacoor, Cavite, within the stationery and décor industry. The research evaluates the viability of the planned business using financial predictions, demand-supply analysis, and market survey data. The proponents used factual data for informative parts and used primary data in answering questions that arise during research. About 96.73% of respondents indicated that they would be willing to buy the goods, indicating great market approval. Favorable entry conditions are further supported by a substantial demand-supply gap. Financial forecasts show high contribution margins and consistent revenue growth. The proponents discovered that their target market would consider buying the product and would consider preferring the company over existing stationary companies in the market. ClipMark offers a feasible business opportunity that is backed by efficient marketing techniques and inexpensive production methods. The proponents realized that if ever they were to pursue to operate this company and to produce the product, there is a great opportunity that awaits them in the stationery and décor industry.

Keywords: Paper clip; Stationery; Décor industry; Marketing techniques; Office products.

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Introduction

In recent years, purchasing behavior has been greatly impacted by the growing need for creative and visually appealing consumer goods. Customers in the stationery sector are looking for products that mix functionality, style, and adaptability rather than only functional things (Han & Ma, 2017; Ribbeck-Lampel, 2020). School-age consumers whose handwriting skills are still developing and those with limited computing or technology-related skills use stationery products extensively. Most significantly, stationery is preferred over uniform computerized productions in situations where pen and paper products are associated with artistic value and emotional connections such as special design stationery items or handmade products (Aurmanarom, 2010). According to Tu et al. (2018), the stationery sector can create creative writing stationery supplies that meet the needs of office workers by understanding the differences in the lives of office workers and their preferences for different types of writing stationery.

Economic progress depends heavily on entrepreneurship, especially when it comes to small-scale inventions that solve unmet customer demands (Andries & Czarnitski, 2014). The retailer's position has evolved from that of a passive distributor to that of an active middleman who carefully chooses products from manufacturers to control the product range offered (Varley, 2014). A business could be born medium-sized or even large, but they are not always born little from the start (von Wobeser, 2016). Differentiation through functionality and design is crucial for business success in cutthroat industries like stationery (Dasayanaka et al., 2017; Teufel & Zimmerman, 2015). Because of the physical characteristics of the items that are part of the paper goods, standard distribution to customers and retail purchasers in the gift business still takes place on both online and offline platforms (Lynch, 2018).

Recently, people have been more interested in using and collecting stationary products. Consumers, from students to office workers, often invest in the products they use for stationery and organizers. Unique and aesthetically pleasing products are in trend for their appeal and how "Instagram worthy" they are. According to Tan (2020), cultural and creative product design must ascertain the demands of the user, define the features and functions of the product in accordance with the needs, and then develop a conceptual design plan based on demand analysis. The outcome of organizing and analyzing attractive characteristics can give stationery stores or related industries more insightful recommendations and make them more appealing to customers (Han & Ma, 2018).

This trend also made its way to the household as consumers who are home décor conscious now opt for aesthetically pleasing products aside from their usefulness. Nowadays, people seek home products that could double as décors when not used, both for design purposes and practicality. With these trends in mind, the researchers come up with the product ClipMark.

ClipMark is an innovation derived from an everyday tool that is used by students, office workers and homemakers. It is a book sized paperclip and one with stand, that can be utilized in different tasks in the workplace and in the household. ClipMark can be used for the following purposes: as a bookmark, paperweight, paperclip, note holder and book organizer. This study aims to evaluate the business feasibility of ClipMark by analyzing its market potential, competitive positioning, marketing strategy, and financial viability.

Methodology

This study used a descriptive feasibility research design that integrated both quantitative and qualitative data to evaluate company viability. A structured survey was used to gather primary data from 397 respondents in Molino III, Bacoor, Cavite. Financial forecasts, market data, and population figures were examples of secondary data. Using Slovin's formula and a 5% margin of error, the sample size was calculated, yielding 397 responses out of a population of 59,039. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage), demand and supply projections, and financial forecasting (sales, costs, and income statements).

In terms of demographics, this product is suitable for ages 16 to 60 years old. Students, office workers, and homemakers would find our product most useful among other occupations as they directly work with stationary products and hangers. The product is budget-friendly, and it is not limited to any income level. The company only has one indirect competitor, since there is no company that produces the same product. The company's indirect competitor in paper clip manufacturing is Best Buy because they sell paper clips worldwide and their brand is much known for other school and office supplies. Best Buy Co., Inc. is an American multinational consumer electronics retailer headquartered in Richfield, Minnesota. It was originally founded by Richard M. Schulze and James Wheeler in 1966 as an audio specialty store called Sound of Music. In 1983, it was rebranded under its current name with more emphasis placed on consumer electronics.

Results and Discussion

Survey Analysis

Table 1. Occupation of respondents (n=397)

Choices	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Student	146	36.78%	2
Office Worker	164	41.31%	1
Housewife/husband	87	21.91%	3

Table 1 reveals the occupation of respondents. This shows that most of the respondents under the target market are office workers (41.31%). This data would help the company in making customer driven strategies. The company would formulate strategies that are aligned with the needs and preference of mostly office workers than of other occupations of the target market.

Table 2. Survey questions for individual consumers

Questions	Choices	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1. How often do you buy paper clips?	Once a week	64	16.12%	2
	Once a month	311	78.34%	1
	Every six months	14	3.53%	3
	Every year	8	2.02%	4
2. Where do you buy your stationary products?	Schools	192	48.36%	1
	Malls	49	12.34%	3
	Commercial areas near you	156	39.29%	2
3. For what purpose/s do you often use your paper clip?	Document compiling	397	100.00%	1
	Bookmarks	197	49.62%	2
	Keeping notes	124	31.23%	3
4. What color do you prefer when buying a product?	Red	174	43.83%	4
	Blue	122	30.73%	7
	Green	53	13.35%	10
	Black	231	58.19%	3
	Gold	397	100%	1
	Violet	154	38.79%	5
	Pink	134	33.75%	6
	Yellow	93	23.43%	8
	Orange	77	19.4%	9
Silver	269	67.76%	2	
5. Does a product's aesthetic appeal affect your buying decision?	Yes	301	75.82%	1
	No	96	24.18%	2
6. How much do you spend on buying paper clips?	Below ₱10	41	10.33%	2
	₱10 to ₱50	356	89.67%	1
7. Do you often create and/or receive notes as a form of reminder for important tasks?	Yes	335	84.38%	1
	No	62	15.62%	2
8. Would you consider buying innovative products like oversized paperclips?	Yes	384	96.73%	1
	No	13	3.27%	2
9. Would you consider buying paper clips that can be used with a stand?	Yes	294	74.06%	1
	No	103	25.94%	2
10. Do you prefer the stand to be built in or detachable?	Detachable	257	64.74%	1
	Built-in	140	35.26%	2
11. What material would you prefer our ClipMark's stand be made of?	Wood	336	84.63%	1
	Metal	61	15.37%	2
12. If you were to buy a ClipMark, how much are you willing to pay for a piece?	₱50 to ₱59	61	15.37%	3
	₱60 to ₱69	122	30.73%	2
	₱70 and above	214	53.9%	1

Table 2 determines the survey questions for individual consumers. Most respondents, 311 or 78.34% of them, often buy their paper clips once a month. The answers gathered that most people often replenish their paper clip supply twelve times a year, this will now be the basis for the production and

inventory strategy. The company shall produce products aligned with this and make sure to have enough supply for the demand. The table shows that most of the respondents buy their stationery, primarily from their schools and commercial areas that have stores selling school/stationary supplies. The company would base from this and position the product on schools if possible and on commercial areas inside communities, for the product to be easily accessible to the consumers. Students, office workers, and homemakers of Molino III often use their paper clips for compiling their paperwork and documents as bookmarks. The company must align the functions and attributes of the product for documenting and bookmarking purposes for intensive customer satisfaction.

The respondents have a variety of color choices for our proposed products, and the results shone light to what they preferred most. The top five (5) colors the respondents chose are gold, silver, black, red, and violet. Hence, this is the reason why the company chose to produce the product in those colors for variants. Meanwhile, the answers of the respondents made it clear that the aesthetic appeal of a product is a factor that influences most of the consumer's value perception and buying decision. This helped the proponents understand that the aesthetic appeal of the ClipMark should shine among others for competitive advantage. The price that the majority of the respondents pay for a normal paper clip ranges from ten pesos to fifty pesos. This data will be surely taken into consideration in the pricing strategy as it is a vital information regarding the consumers spending pattern.

People under the scope of occupation mostly create and/or receive important notes that remind them of a task or event they need to do or attend. This indicates that there is a demand for the product and that the proponents should target. When asked if the respondents are willing to buy the product ClipMark, the result came out very positive. Three-hundred and eighty-four (384) or 94.73% of the respondents agreed that they would buy ClipMark when launched. The respondents did not only consider buying ClipMark but they also considered buying it with a stand to use. This data is the basis of the decision in making a stand for the product.

Since the majority of the respondents, 257 people or 64.74%, prefer the stand to be detachable, the company will have its stand be made that way to satisfy the consumers and ensure market acceptability. The consideration for the material to be used for the stand was two: wood and metal. The majority of the respondents chose wood over metal with 84.63%. This data helped the proponents to finalize the decision. The price of the product was based from the expenses and markup computation aligned with the result of this question. Most respondents are willing to pay seventy pesos and above for the product offered. Hence, the proponents of the study decided it was just to launch the product within this price range.

Demand

The company did a thorough research regarding the population of the target barangay to have accurate data for the population and demand projections. These projections would help the proponents create strategies and decisions that would cater to the consumers' needs and would satisfy their preferences.

Table 3. Historical Household Population

Year	Household Population	Growth rate (%)
2016	58,757	0.0016%
2017	58,851	0.0016%
2018	58,945	0.0016%

Table 3 shows the historical household population. According to the data, from 2016 to 2018, the household population of Molino III, Bacoor City, Cavite, increased very slightly yet steadily. The population grew by just 0.0016% annually, from 58,757 in 2016 to 58,851 in 2017 and 58,945 in 2018. This incredibly low growth rate suggests that the population of the area was largely steady over this time,

with only slight annual increases. This could be due to low birth rates, little migration, or a balance between people moving in and out of the town.

Table 4. Projected Population for five (5) years

Year	Household Growth Rate (%)	Household Growth per year	Projected Population
2018			58,945
2019	0.0016	94	59,039
2020	0.0016	94	59,133
2021	0.0016	95	59,228
2022	0.0016	95	59,323
2023	0.0016	95	59,418

Table 4 reveals the projected population for five (5) years. Based on a stable growth rate of 0.0016% annually, the predicted population data for Molino III, Bacoor City, Cavite from 2019 to 2023 shows a steady but extremely moderate increase in household population. From a base population of 58,945 in 2018, the population is projected to increase gradually every year, adding roughly 94 to 95 people every year. The population is expected to grow to 59,418 by 2023. This pattern shows a steady and predictable growth trend, indicating that the region is seeing slow and controllable population increases throughout time rather than fast urban expansion.

Table 5. Projected Demand

Year	Projected Annual Demand	Growth rate (%)
2019	44,699	
2020	44,740	0.0009
2021	44,780	0.0009
2022	44,820	0.0009
2023	44,860	0.0009

Projected Annual Demand = Household X Market Acceptability X Frequency 2019 Projected

Annual Demand = 59,039 x 97% x 78%

2019 Projected Annual Demand = 44,699

2020 Projected Annual Demand = 59,133 x 97% x 78%

2020 Projected Annual Demand = 44,740

Table 5 shows the projected demand. The demand is expected to rise extremely gradually and steadily between 2019 and 2023. The demand starts at 44,699 in 2019 and increases marginally every year until it reaches 44,860 by 2023. The rise is only roughly 40–41 units annually due to the low yearly growth rate of 0.0009%. This suggests that consumption or service demands in the area are developing slowly and predictably, perhaps in accordance with the modest population growth and without any external influences pushing rapid change. It also shows a stable demand pattern with few changes.

Supply

Table 6. Historical Supply of Best Buy for three (3) years

Year	Supply	Growth Rate
2016	15,300	3.3%
2017	16,400	7.1%
2018	22,500	37%
Total		15.8% = 16%

Table 6 indicates a historical supply of Best Buy for three (3) years. Best Buy’s supply data from 2016 to 2018 demonstrates a notable rising trend with faster increase across the three years. From 15,300 in 2016 to 16,400 in 2017, supply grew at a moderate rate of 3.3% and 7.1%, respectively. But in 2018, there was a dramatic surge, with supply reaching 22,500—a significant 37% increase. The average growth rate is estimated at around 16%, indicating that supply expansion became much more aggressive in the final year. This pattern points to a significant drive to expand operations or meet rising demand, especially between 2017 and 2018.

Table 7. Projected Supply for five (5) years for Best Buy

Year	Supply Rate	Supply per Year	Projected Supply
2018			22,500
2019	0.0016	36	22,536
2020	0.0016	36	22,572
2021	0.0016	36	22,608
2022	0.0016	36	22,644
2023	0.0016	36	22,680

Table 7 shows the projected supply for five (5) years for Best Buy. Best Buy’s supply is expected to grow extremely slowly and steadily between 2019 and 2023 after a significantly greater increase in 2018. The supply is predicted to increase by just over 36 units annually from a base supply of 22,500 in 2018 to 22,680 by 2023. This trend indicates that supply expansion has steadied following the notable spike in 2018, with a minimum annual growth rate of 0.0016%. Future increases are anticipated to be gradual and under control. This could mean that growth is being carefully controlled to prevent overstock, or that supply has already reached a level enough to fulfill demand.

Demand and Supply Gap

Table 8. Demand and Supply Gap

Year	Demand	Supply	Demand-Supply Gap	Market Share (14%)
2019	44,699	22,536	22,163	3,102.82
2020	44,740	22,572	22,168	3,103.52
2021	44,780	22,608	22,172	3,104.08
2022	44,820	22,644	22,176	3,104.64
2023	44,860	22,680	22,180	3,105.02

Table 8 reveals the demand and supply gap. Between 2019 and 2023, the difference between supply and demand was generally substantial and somewhat growing. While supply grows much more slowly, from 22,536 to 22,680 during the same period, demand rises gradually from 44,699 in 2019 to 44,860 in 2023. Because of this, the difference is still large, slightly increasing from 22,163 to 22,180, showing that supply is not keeping up with demand over time. Notwithstanding this disparity, the anticipated 14% market share also exhibits a modest yearly growth, indicating a steady chance to seize some of the unfulfilled demand. The data shows a sustained shortage of supply, which may create an environment that is conducive to growth of new competitors.

Table 9 indicates a market share for Best Buy. From 2019 to 2023, the market share data from Best Buy indicates a very small but steady increase over time. Despite the fact that both supply (Best Buy’s output) and overall demand are progressively increasing year, supply growth is consistent enough to sustain and slightly increase its market share. The calculated market share numbers show a stable position with little annual growth, rising from 3,102.82 in 2019 to 3,105.02 in 2023. This pattern indicates a somewhat balanced but under-saturated environment where more development prospects may still exist, even though Best Buy is keeping up with demand without increasing its market domination.

Table 9. Market Share

Market Share	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Best Buy	22,536	22,572	22,608	22,644	22,680
Divided: Total Demand	44,699	44,740	44,780	44,820	44,860
Market Share: Best Buy	3,102.82	3,103.52	3,104.08	3,104.64	3,105.02

Table 10. Price Breakdown

Variable Cost	
Steel wire	13
Paint	4.17
Paper bag	12
Total Material Cost	29.17
Direct Labor	2,400
Production unit volume	240
Direct labor in units	10
Total Variable Cost	39.17
Fixed Cost	
Rent	3,000
Salaries	15,000
Utilities	8,300
Total Fixed Cost	26,300
Production	240
Total Fixed Cost (units)	110
Total Cost	148.13
Desired Selling Price	250
Less: Variable Cost	39.17
Total Contribution Margin (units)	210.83
Total Contribution Margin (units)	210.83
divided by Desired Selling Price	250
Total Contribution Margin %	84.3%

Table 10 indicates the price breakdown of the product. According to the cost structure, the manufacture of the product entails a total variable cost of ₱39.17 per unit, which comprises direct labor and materials, while fixed expenses are ₱26,300, or ₱110 per unit based on a production volume of 240 units. As a result, each unit costs ₱148.13 in total. The contribution margin is ₱210.83 per unit at a target selling price of ₱250, resulting in an extremely high contribution margin ratio of 84.3%. Given that a significant amount of the selling price goes toward paying fixed costs and making a profit, this suggests substantial potential profitability. Overall, the numbers indicate that the company would generate significant margins and financial sustainability if the product could be sold at the desired price.

Marketing Program (4P's)

Product. ClipMark, is an innovation derived from an everyday tool that is used by students, office workers and homemakers. It is a book sized paperclip and one with stand that can be utilized in different tasks in the workplace and in the household.

Price. The company made pricing decisions for the product, by calculating the expenses for the materials used and the salary we spend for labor. The sum of the expense for the materials used is Php76.67 and Php6.00 for labor, because the company pays 300 per production day for 50pieces. Based from the variables mentioned and with the markup added the proponents have finalized the price.

Place. The company positioned its product in the heart of Camella Springville's business center, where the main traffic of people takes place, for it to be easily accessible to consumers especially to our target market. Hence, the proponents decided to distribute the product in that location as it is surrounded by schools and business firms.

Promotion. The marketing strategies were divided into two; strategies for Business to business (B2B) marketing and strategies for Business to customer (B2) marketing. We divided our strategies to make sure that all marketing activities are effective and efficient. The strategies were strategically assigned to avoid unnecessary spending of funds.

Marketing Strategies

Strategies for Business to Business Marketing

Being updated with all networking events is a huge advantage for businesses especially to small time businesses like the company's. These events often gather businesses from same industries and because of that, the chance of finding partners, suppliers and/or manufacturers would be higher than trying to find those on own.

Businesspeople who attend said events are people with connections all over different industries and tapping those connections would be beneficial for the company. Face to face interactions creates a more stable business relationship. It also serves as a bonus that topics and updates about the industry is usually discussed in said events. Below is an example.

Obtaining the clients' attention and interest is very crucial in selling the product. In this method, businesses catch the prospect's attention even before the prospect feels a need to buy a product. Using inbound marketing, the company will lure the consumer by content marketing thoroughly. Once the attention of the customers are caught, the company will proceed to showing how beneficial the product is and focus on turning strangers to customers.

Strategies for Business to Customer Marketing

Print Media Marketing. Upon the start of operations of the business, posters and tarpaulins will be posted around Molino III and St. Dominic College of Asia. Traditional marketing may be old, but its effectiveness is tested and proven through time. The company will create enticing formats for posters and tarpaulins containing information regarding updates and promotions. Below are the content we will produce through print media.

Direct Marketing. Marketing and selling the product directly to consumers is the most basic marketing strategy and still one of the most crucial. Knowing how to present and sell the products directly is something the company should know how to do when starting a business. Through booths and joining business exposition the company seeks to make its mark in the market and boost its product's name in the industry.

Word of Mouth. This marketing strategy may be unpaid by the company, but it is very powerful. The talk around the market regarding your product impacts on its image more than any business could control. Making sure that people are spreading positive feedback instead of negative is a huge task that marketers and business owners must keep on doing. Through satisfying consumers and making sure their needs and preferences are met is one way of securing a positive word of mouth about the product and company.

Relationship Marketing. In this strategy, the company will focus more on retaining customer loyalty and maintaining long term relationships with our customers. Marketing Programs for after sales marketing and customer service would be created in lined with the data that we gathered and will gather. Personal marketing is one of the factors the business would apply under this strategy, making sure that customers are accounted individually is a sure way to gain loyalty. Contents of the posts, both on social media and print media, would also tackle issues that are relevant to assure consumers that the company cares sincerely for all.

Transactional Marketing. Through this strategy, the company will take the direct selling/marketing to the next level. Giving out discounts, coupons and rebates are all under this strategy. These promotional discounts would encourage walk-in customers to buy the products and possibly in bigger quantities for practicality. Promotions like aforementioned will be done periodically and will be strategically scheduled on paydays, holidays, and special events.

Social Media Marketing. The social media platform has become the biggest platform yet in the business industry and being left behind from this trend could cause serious setbacks and disadvantages to a company. The company will be active on different social media sites to update the consumers of the happenings regarding the business. Announcements about the promotions and activities would be posted in formats for attention and variety. Becoming viral on social media a boost a company’s brand image by ten folds and that’s why we plan on creating content that are suitable with the current trends and current viral contents. The company plans to retain its social media presence by posting not only weekly, but also when there is opportunity to go viral or seen by a lot of netizens. A SWOT analysis was made in Table 11.

Table 11. SWOT Analysis

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New and innovative product • It is multi-functional • The product is easy to produce • Low cost of production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product development is limited due to the budget • Struggles in penetrating the industry as a new business
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raw materials are not scarce and easy to avail 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changes in the mining industry • People may not be interested or willing to risk in buying the product

Socio-Economic Study

Contribution to the Philippine Economy

The Good Life aims to contribute and be of help to the country’s economy by being a responsible private company that focuses not only on success but also on the well-being of society. As a private company, the business will ensure that all of the responsibilities to the government and to the people are all met. The company will thrive to achieve and maintain financial success as it will be beneficial to our government regarding the company’s taxes. The overall success of the company would be of great help to our economy’s growth and development especially in the global market. The company would ensure its success to help the economy’s global standing to increase.

Contribution to the Community

The community is well-valued by the company and its management; The Good Life will go out of its way to provide benefits and opportunities to the people. The company will provide more local jobs for people and will train them to be more competent and productive individuals. The company will also give opportunities to existing business to expand by reselling the products. TGL will be providing locally

made product for not only Filipinos but eventually for a global market. The overall operation would be increasing productivity and innovation in our local community.

Contribution to the Client

The Good Life is a company that focuses and dedicates itself in serving its consumers by providing the product that never been introduced before and helping them achieve a good life. The company would make sure to satisfy the needs and wants of its clients through our product and services.

Contribution to the Industry

The stationary industry is an industry often set aside by people as the products under it is seen common by the people; hence the company would bring growth and innovation to create buzz and increase our industry's image. Through the product, the proponents plan to stimulate economic growth and enlarge the reach of Stationaries nationwide.

Contribution to the Environment

The environment is a factor that all organization cannot control but should be greatly valued. The company understands the importance of the environment deeply and that is why TGL commits to making sure to use raw materials efficiently and minimizing waste. TGL will take responsible actions in our production process to prevent pollution and to prevent any harm or damage to the environment.

Conclusions

The respondents and the target market of the study are consumers who are very open to new businesses and new products. The consumers are willing to try new products as long as they are proven to be worth buying. The company has great potential if ever it is pursued and decides to operate in the industry. The management of the company has developed its readiness for operating through the researches done in this feasibility study; The product is accepted by the target market and is proven to have great potential among direct and indirect competitors. Through the results of the studies conducted, the product can be ready for commercialization if pursued.

Recommendations

For the customers, the proponents suggest to keep their standards in mind and the convenience of the products, but do not hesitate to risk and try something that is new to the eyes. For continuous growth and development, there shall be continuous change in giving chance to those companies and products that are just starting out. The proponents recommend further development within the venture. They advised serving the consumers to never forget to align the decisions and actions to the company's goals and do things not only for themselves, but for the betterment of the company, the economy and society.

For the community, they should support local businesses and never be afraid to explore the market for options. The economy of the country does not only depend on businesses like us but also on the community's buying decisions and behavior. For the subordinates, they should maintain a positive attitude to maintain a great working environment for all employees. Holistic development should be as important as your performance in the office. Work does not only work intelligently but also with passion.

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